

STUDY ON THE ATTITUDE ON MORAL JUDGEMENT OF HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS

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Abstract:

The present study aims at probing the attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students with regard to gender, locality, type of school, and parental education. Normative survey was conducted on a sample of 250 students, selected from nine higher secondary schools in Villupuram District, Tamil Nadu. Moral Judgment Questionnaire, constructed and standardized by Shaji Vellikkattukunnel (2005), was used to measure the moral judgment of higher secondary students. The collected data were tabulated and analyzed with the help of IBM SPSS version 16.0. Findings show that that level of attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students is moderate and there is no significant difference in the attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students with regard to gender, locality, type of school, and parental education.

Key Words: Attitude, Moral Judgement & Higher Secondary Students

Introduction:

Value based education among the students all over the world is a matter of concern and priority. In the olden days, value based education was taught through Vedas and Upanishads in the Gurugula system of education in India. Value based education helps to bring out the overall development and creates the good citizen for the nation. According to Piaget (1966) "All morality consists in a system of rules and the essence of all morality is to be sought in the respect which the individual acquires for these rules". The meaning of morality can be viewed in different perspectives like individual, societal, national and international. Moral judgment refers to the process in which an individual decides what is morally right or wrong. It is a complex issue and even educated people are finding it difficult to judge and are unable to solve their own problems. Shukla (1983) says "The gulf between the rich and the poor, the educated and the uneducated, the tolerance and selfishness that are widely prevalent". The failure of education to impart right knowledge and skills to enable majority of students to lead economically independent lives, the rampant unrest among students and their tendency to violate values, the un-rootedness of the educated in their own tradition, culture and values.

Review of Related Studies:

Kumar (2017) conducted a study on moral judgment of B.Ed. student teachers in relation to their social maturity at Mysore city and found that the female student teachers have high morality than their male counter parts. Walker, Thoma, Jones, & Kristjansson (2017) conducted a study on adolescent moral judgement: a study of UK secondary school pupils and found that significantly and positively associated with being female, having a religion and doing specific extra-curricular activities. Upadhyaya (2015) conducted a study on gender difference in moral judgment among secondary level students at Allahabad city and found that female students had high moral judgment as compared to their male counterparts. Keskin (2013) examined the Secondary school students' moral Judgement competencies: a comparison between Samsun-Turkey and Lancashire-England and found that there was no significant difference in scores of moral value judgment in either of the two countries. Sucharitha (2012) conducted a study of moral judgement of higher secondary students in relation to some variables and found that that sex has no influence on moral judgement of students.

Significance of the Study:

According to psychologists the moral development starts at the age of two and exponentially develops between 8 and 18 age. Family and the school are the social organization where the good habits and values are nurtured in a child. The role of parent and the teachers are vital in imparting the value education during the childhood stage. They are not only the teaches and also the role model in cultivating the good habits and values such as love, sharing, living together, tolerance, respecting elders, obedience, honesty, kindness etc. among the students. Values are to be taught formally and informally. The students should be given opportunity to learn the basic and essential values to prepare themselves for the future as ideal citizen of the county. Adolescence is the stage of storms and stresses. During this stage, they have confused minds in judging the moral values and selecting right or wrong in their life in chaotic situations. So the author felt the need for conducting this study to find out the attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students.

Title of the Study:

A Study on the Attitude on Moral Judgement of Higher Secondary Students

Operational Definition of the Key Terms:

- **Attitude:** It is the feeling or opinion about moral judgement of higher secondary students.

- **Moral Judgment:** It is the ability to learn the difference between right or wrong and understand how to make the right choices.
- **Higher Secondary Students:** It refers to the students who are studying in standards XI and XII in higher secondary schools of Villupuram District, Tamil Nadu.

Objectives:

- To find out the level of attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students
- To find out the level of attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students with regard to gender, locality, type of school, and parental education.

Hypotheses:

- H₀1: There is no significant difference in the attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students with regard to gender.
- H₀2: There is no significant difference in the attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students with regard to locality.
- H₀3: There is no significant difference in the attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students with regard to type of school.
- H₀4: There is no significant difference in the attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students with regard to parental education.

Methodology:

In the present study, normative survey method was employed. A sample of 250 students who studied in the standards XI and XII in nine higher secondary schools in Villupuram District, Tamil Nadu were selected for the study. The Moral Judgment Questionnaire which was constructed and standardized by Shaji Vellikkattukunnel (2005) was used to measure the moral judgment of higher secondary students. The tool has 15 questions pertaining to moral judgement. Each question is taken from different life situations and the respondents have to indicate their choice by putting a tick-mark against any one of the four choices and each correct statement is given the score 4. Thus the maximum score of the tool is 60 and the minimum is 0. Test re-test method was used for establishing reliability of moral judgment questionnaire and it was found to be 0.85 showing a high reliability. The collected data were tabulated and analyzed with the help of IBM SPSS version 16.0.

Analysis of Data:

Objective Testing:

To find out the level of attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students

Table 1: Level of Attitude on Moral Judgement of Higher Secondary Students

Low		Moderate		High	
N	%	N	%	N	%
83	33.2	158	63.2	9	3.6

Figure 1: Level of Attitude on Moral Judgement of Higher Secondary Students

It is inferred from the above table that 33.2% of higher secondary students have low, 63.2% of them have moderate, and 3.6% of them have high level of attitude on moral judgement. Thus, the level of attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students is moderate.

Hypotheses Testing:

H₀1: There is no significant difference in the attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students with regard to gender.

Table 2: Difference in the Attitude on Moral Judgement of Higher Secondary Students with regard to Gender

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Calculated t-value	Table t-value	Significant Level
Attitude	Boys	183	27.0383	10.58890	1.074	1.96	Not Significant
	Girls	67	28.5970	8.86953			

Figure 2: Difference in the Mean Scores of the Attitude on Moral Judgement of Higher Secondary Boys and Girls

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated t-value (1.074) is lesser than the table t-value (1.96) at 5% level of significance. Therefore, it is concluded that null hypothesis is accepted and there is no significant difference in the attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students with regard to gender.

H₀2: There is no significant difference in the attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students with regard to locality.

Table 3: Difference in the Attitude on Moral Judgement of Higher Secondary Students with regard to Locality

Variable	Locality	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Calculated t-value	Table t-value	Significant Level
Attitude	Village	114	28.2105	8.85425	1.042	1.96	Not Significant
	Town	136	26.8235	11.13545			

Figure 3: Difference in the Mean Scores of the Attitude on Moral Judgement of Higher Secondary Village and Town students

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated t-value (1.042) is lesser than the table t-value (1.96) at 5% level of significance. Therefore, it is concluded that null hypothesis is accepted and there is no significant difference in the attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students with regard to locality.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students with regard to type of school.

Table 4: Difference in the Attitude on Moral Judgement of Higher Secondary Students with regard to type of school

	Type of School	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Calculated t-value	Table t-value	Significant Level
Attitude	Government School	233	27.5536	10.24223	0.562	1.96	Not Significant
	Private School	17	26.1176	9.17798			

Figure 4: Difference in the Mean Scores of the Attitude on Moral Judgement of Government and Private Higher Secondary School Students

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated t-value (0.562) is lesser than the table t-value (1.96) at 5% level of significance. Therefore, it is concluded that null hypothesis is accepted and there is no significant difference in the attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students with regard to type of school.

H₀₄: There is no significant difference in the attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students with regard to parental education.

Table 5: Difference in the Attitude on Moral Judgement of Higher Secondary Students with regard to Parental Education

	Parental Education	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Calculated t-value	Table t-value	Significant Level
Attitude	Literate	140	26.3714	10.01750	1.853	1.96	Not Significant
	Illiterate	108	28.7778	10.29593			

Figure 5: Difference in the Mean Scores of Attitude on Moral Judgement of Higher Secondary Students with regard to Parental Education

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated t-value (1.853) is lesser than the table t-value (1.96) at 5% level of significance. Therefore, it is concluded that null hypothesis is accepted and there is no significant difference in the attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students with regard to parental education.

Findings and Discussion:

From this study, it is found out that the level of attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students is moderate. At the same time, only 3.6% of the secondary students have high and 33.2% of them have low level of attitude on moral judgement. The attitude on moral judgement is less among the secondary students and this may be due to the non-availability of moral education at school level and the expanding modern social progress without the value of humanism.

From the t-test, it is concluded that there is no significant difference in the attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students with regard to gender. While comparing the mean scores, girls (28.5970) are found to be better than the higher secondary boys (27.0383) in their attitude on moral judgement. This may be due to the fact that the girls take up the taught-morality with greater care than the boys, right from their childhood onwards in our society. Hence, the girls have a high level of attitude on moral judgement.

There is no significant difference in the attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students with regard to locality. While comparing the mean scores, village students (28.2105) are found to be better than the town students (26.8235) in their attitude on moral judgement. This may be due to the fact that joint families are more in villages and therefore the students receive moral education from their grandparents. Hence, village students may have positive attitude on moral judgement.

There is no significant difference in the attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students with regard to type of school. While comparing the mean scores, government school students (27.5536) are found to be better than the private school students (26.1176) in their attitude on moral judgement. This may be due to the fact that the private school students, being rich may have been given more pampered that leads to indulge in immoral activities. Hence, government school students may have positive a high attitude on moral judgement.

There is no significant difference in the attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students with regard to parental education. While comparing the mean scores, illiterate parents' children (28.7778) are better than the literate parents' children (26.3714) in their attitude on moral judgement. This may be due to the fact that illiterate parents bring up their children with more discipline and control in a cultural background. Hence, illiterate parents' children may have positive attitude on moral judgement.

Conclusion:

It is concluded that level of attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students is moderate suggesting the need to raise this level. No significant difference in the attitude on moral judgement of higher secondary students with regard to gender, locality, type of school, and parental education was found suggesting that both are equal in their attitude. The total mean score (27.456) of the higher secondary students in Villupuram district is below average than median score. Hence, the moral education should be taught at school level and it is very essential in order to enhance the morality of the higher secondary students. The high level of attitude inferred based on the mean scores of girls, village students, government school students and children of illiterate parents supports the belief of the common man, adding significance and value to the study.

References:

1. Keskin, Yakup. (2013). Secondary school students' moral judgement competencies: a comparison between Samsun-Turkey and Lancashire-England. *Ondokuz Mayıs Univ. Egitim Fakultesi*, 32, 217-249. doi: 10.7822/egt224.
2. Kumar, S. C. R. (2017). Moral judgment of B.Ed student teachers in relation to their social maturity. *International Journal of Research - Granthaalayah*, 5(9), 250-265. Retrieved from <http://oaji.net/articles/2017/1330-1508837487.pdf>
3. Piaget, Jean (1966). *The moral judgment of the child*. New York: Free Press.
4. Shukla, R.P. (1983). What is wrong with our education? *School Education*, 10 (4), 30.
5. Sucharitha, R. (2012). A study of moral judgement of higher secondary students in relation to some variables. [Unpublished Doctoral Thesis]. Sri Padmavati Mahila Visva Vidyalayam, Tirupati, India.
6. Upadhyaya, Pratik (2015). Gender difference in moral judgment among secondary level students. *International Journal of Research – Granthaalayah*, 3 (11), 17-20. Retrieved from http://granthaalayah.com/Articles/Vol3Iss11/03_IJRG15_C11_23.pdf
7. Walker, D., Thoma, S., Jones, C., & Kristjansson, K. (2017). Adolescent moral judgement: A study of UK secondary school pupils. *British Educational Research Journal*. 10.1002/berj.3274.